

👋 Zoom-o-mat-o-poe-ia

A small collective exercise for Zoom. A play with voices and the meeting interface.

Zoom Exercise

Interface Performance

Takes 5–10 min. Best in medium to large size groups.

Exercise Script

1. First, we will all change our name in Zoom.

[Explain how to do it]

(Via the option button with the three dots on their own camera image or the options button in the participants list.)

2. Think of a word with one to three syllables for your new name. Something that doesn't really have a meaning to you and that doesn't name a thing. A word that is mostly a sound.

Like "hui" or "pico" or "kawau" or "ching". A sound/word you like or that fits your mood. Really anything you choose will be good.

You have 15 seconds to decide for your new name. [Wait for everyone]

3. Now, everyone switch off your cameras.

(This will only show the chosen words in each participants' frame. That's why short words are good, so they don't get cropped in the interface.)

4. I will now read out the words as I see them on my screen, starting in the top left. You may see a different sequence on your screen, but follow along in your mind.

5. [Read out the sequence]

(With steady confidence, or as dramatically as you wish.)

6. Maybe it reads different for you. Does anyone would want to read the version on their screen? Please, just go ahead.

(Cameras are still off. If you like, ask for a few more individual readings.)

7. Now, let's do one further escalation. Everyone, "raise your hand" in Zoom.

[Explain how to do it]

(Via the "Reactions" button at the bottom. This will rearrange everyone's screen in the order each one raised their hand.)

[Wait for everyone's hand up]

8. If everything worked out, our screens should be in the same order now.

9. Let's read it out together, at the same time.

If you can and just if you want, unmute your mic now. Read out loud, whatever you see on your screen. Again starting from the top left. Just keep going, no matter what.

On the count of three: 1... 2... 3...

10. [Read in chorus]

The exercise can create a refreshingly simple moment of collective creation and shared attention. Choosing a sound-word is engaging without much pressure for any meaning or quality. Cameras off can create a lower bar to participate and read along. It shifts the focus away from the dominant visuality of the video platform for a moment to bring attention to the sound of voices. The exercise might also help to ease "first thing I said in a meeting" anxieties and make people get comfortable to hear their voice "in the room" in a playful way. It subtly subverts the authority or familiarity of the meeting software interface ("we don't need to rely on video, the name tag is just a text field we can repurpose, ..."). And it creates a delightful messiness in the chat, if people don't change their names back afterwards.

. . .

Developed for and first tested in an online workshop with the Critical Media Lab Basel on 2 February 2022.